

MICRO-SCALE SIMULATION FOR NONLINEAR STRESS–STRAIN BEHAVIOR OF UNIDIRECTIONAL CARBON FIBER/ PHENYL–ETHYNYL TERMINATED POLYIMIDE TRIA-X COMPOSITES

Tatsuya Kobayashi ¹, Satoru Yoshikawa ¹, Toshio Ogasawara ¹
Yuichi Ishida ², Mio Sato ², Masahiko Miyauchi ³

¹ Tokyo University of Agriculture and Technology,
2-24-16 Naka-cho, Koganei-shi, 184-8588, Tokyo, Japan
Email: s252316r@st.go.tuat.ac.jp, ogasat@cc.tuat.ac.jp

² Japan Aerospace Exploration Agency (JAXA),
6-13-1 Osawa, Mitaka-shi, 181-0015, Tokyo, Japan

³ Kaneka Co.,
5-1-1 Torikainishi, Setsu-shi, 566-0072, Osaka, Japan

Keywords: Polymer-matrix composites (PMCs), Thermosetting resin, Mechanical properties, Analytical modelling, High-temperature properties

ABSTRACT

TriA-X, a phenylethynyl-terminated polyimide resin with a Kapton-type structure, has a glass transition temperature of 350°C or higher and is a promising matrix resin for heat-resistant CFRP (Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics). This study attempted to predict the mechanical behavior of carbon fiber/TriA-X composites (CF/TriA-X) using micro-scale analysis. Based on the experimentally obtained mechanical properties of the cured resin, the constitutive model for linear viscoelasticity and viscoplasticity were applied individually, and the time and temperature dependent mechanical behaviors were taken into consideration. The viscoelastic parameters were determined from the results of creep tests without residual strain, while the viscoplastic parameters were obtained by subtracting the viscoelastic strain from the total strain of the creep tests that produced residual strain. Using microscale models consisting of fiber and matrix, the nonlinear mechanical behavior of unidirectional CF/TriA-X (UD-CFRP) under off axis tension was calculated using finite element analysis code Digimat FE (Hexagon) considering the viscoelastic and viscoplastic behavior. As a result, the stress-strain curves of off-axis UD-CF/TriA-X composites at room temperature were in good agreement with the experimental results.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, carbon fiber reinforced plastic composites (CFRP), which have high specific strength and stiffness, were widely applied to airframe structures to reduce aircraft weight and maintenance costs. Most of the CFRP for aircrafts consists of an epoxy resin matrix, with operating heat resistance temperatures limited to 120°C. By contrast, CFRP consisting of heat-resistant resins such as bismaleimide and polyimide have higher operating temperature of 200 to 300°C, which is superior to that of epoxy resins. Among heat-resistant resins, polyimide resin has a high glass transition temperature (T_g), excellent mechanical properties, chemical stability, and low thermal expansion coefficient. Therefore, it is expected to be used as a matrix resin for heat-resistant CFRP to be applied to parts requiring high heat resistance, such as turbofan engine parts and the airframe of supersonic aircrafts, which have been difficult to apply with conventional epoxy-based CFRP [1-3].

Generally, addition-type (thermosetting type) polyimide resins have high heat resistance, corrosion resistance, mechanical strength, and good moldability, however, they tend to have poor toughness [4]. Furthermore, heat-resistant resins, including polyimide, are generally not easy to mold because it is difficult to obtain low viscosity enough to enable melt molding even in high-temperature environments. To solve this problem, a phenyl-ethynyl terminated addition polyimides (PETI) had been studied, mainly

by NASA. However, the glass transition temperature of typical polyimide resin PETI-5 is only 260-270°C, and it has been difficult for a long time to achieve both heat resistance and mechanical properties [5-9]. Yokota et al. successfully developed for synthesizing an addition-type polyimide (Triple A (TriA) polyimide) with both heat resistance, toughness, and moldability using an asymmetric chemical structure for the polymer main chain. Based on this concept, Miyauchi [6] et al. developed an additive polyimide TriA-X (TripleA-X), having the chemical structure shown in Scheme 1. Cured TriA-X polyimide has high heat resistance and good mechanical properties. TriA-X has higher toughness and heat resistance than conventional polyimide resins, having a softening temperature of 350-370°C and an average strain at break of about 11% for cured resin [10]. TriA-X is expected to be used as a matrix resin for heat-resistant CFRPs, however the mechanical properties of the resin or of composites have not sufficiently understood.

Scheme 1: Chemical structure of TriA-X imide oligomer [6].

Meanwhile, unidirectional CFRP (UD-CFRP) is known to exhibit nonlinear stress-strain behavior because of viscoelastic deformation of matrix resin in the off-axis tensile test. Furthermore, the nonlinear stress-strain behavior of CFRP has time- and temperature-dependence. In polyimide-based CFRP, studies have also been conducted to predict nonlinear behavior by theoretical equations based on experimental results [11]. In structural design using heat-resistant CFRPs, it is necessary to evaluate the mechanical properties at various temperatures, however obtaining material strength data by experimental methods is costly and time-consuming. For this reason, it is expected to establish a technique to predict various mechanical properties of CFRP at a wide range of temperatures based on the properties of resin obtained from experiments.

The aim of this study is to predict the mechanical behavior of UD-CFRP with thermosetting polyimide TriA-X as a matrix at elevated temperatures from the experimentally obtained material properties of matrix resin. In this paper, the mechanical properties of cured neat TriA-X resin are evaluated to model its stress-strain behavior, and the nonlinear mechanical behavior of UD-CFRP is predicted from stress analysis of a unit cell model consisting of fiber and matrix.

2 MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF POLYIMIDE RESIN TRIA-X

2.1 Material and specimen

Cured resin plates were obtained from imide oligomer TriA-X powder ($n=4$). The curing temperature was 370°C. After curing, strip-shaped specimens ($120 \times 10 \times t$ 2.8 [mm³] and $140 \times 10 \times t$ 2 [mm³]) were cut from each resin plate using a cutting machine and provided to tensile testing. The glass transition temperature of the cured resin was about 350°C, obtained from the change in storage modulus by dynamic viscoelasticity (DMA) measurement.

2.2 Experimental procedure

Tensile tests including creep/recovery tests were conducted for cured resin specimens. A servo-hydraulic testing machine (Model 8804, Instron, USA) equipped with a convection type environment chamber (oven) was used for tensile testing. A 5 kN load cell was used to measure the load.

Monotonic tensile tests were conducted under a constant displacement of 1 mm/min until final failure. A contact-type extensometer (Model 633.11C-14, MTS Systems Co.) with a gauge length of 25 mm was used to measure the longitudinal strain. Test temperatures were set to be 23°C, 200°C and 250°C.

Creep/recovery tests were conducted under constant displacement and load-controlled conditions. The holding loads were 20, 30, 40, 60, and 80 MPa, and the time holding was 1 hour, followed by 3 hours of no load (0 MPa). The loading rate up to the holding load was 35 N/min.

Loading/unloading tensile tests were conducted under a constant displacement rate of 0.1 mm/min or 10 mm/min. When the crosshead displacement reached 1, 2, and 3 mm, the load was unloaded to 0 N and then reloaded, respectively. The test temperatures for the creep recovery and loading/unloading tests are 23°C and 200°C, respectively.

2.3 Experimental Result

Stress-strain curves obtained from monotonic tensile testing at 23, 200, and 250°C are shown in Fig. 1, and the initial elastic modulus and strength at break calculated in the strain range 0.05-0.25% are summarized in Table 1. A significant decrease in stiffness with increasing temperature was observed.

Fig. 1: Stress-strain curves of cured TriA-X polyimide specimens.

Table 1: Initial elastic modulus and rupture strength of cured TriA-X.

Temperature	Young modulus [GPa]	Rupture strength [MPa]
RT (23°C)	3.28	78.0
200°C	1.91	58.2
250°C	1.59	45.2

Fig. 2 (a) and (b) present the strain-time curves obtained by the creep/recovery tests. The results show viscoelastic behavior (creep and recovery behavior) at all stress levels [12]. In room temperature, residual strain was not observed at room temperature at holding stresses of 20 and 30 MPa, while residual strain due to viscoplasticity or plasticity was seen at stresses above 40 MPa. It was also confirmed that the creep strain increased with increasing temperature, even at the same holding stress.

Fig. 2: Strain-time curves of cured TriA-X polyimide specimens at 23°C and 200°C.

Fig. 3 (a) and (b) show the stress-strain curves obtained by the loading/unloading tests. Hysteresis behavior in the nonlinear region is observed for all test conditions. Also, the relation between the residual strain after every load-unloading test cycle and the maximum stress during each cycle is depicted in Fig. 4. As shown in Fig. 4, significant residual strain is observed from the third cycle at 23°C and from the second cycle at 200°C. Additionally, residual strain increased rapidly with maximum stress, and the degree of increase was more pronounced at higher temperatures and slower loading rates. The hysteresis behavior and the decrease in stiffness with decreasing loading rate indicate that the resin exhibits remarkable viscoelastic behavior.

Fig. 3: Stress-strain curves of cured TriA-X polyimide specimens at 23°C and 200°C under load/unload tests.

Fig. 4: Residual strain-peak stress curves of cured TriA-X polyimide specimens at RT (23°C) and 200°C under loading/unloading testing.

3 MECHANICAL MODELING OF CURED TRIA-X POLYIMIDE RESIN

3.1 Viscoelastic model

The experimental results of cured TriA-X resin suggest that the nonlinear behavior at room and elevated temperatures cannot be expressed using a simple viscoelastic model. Therefore, strictly speaking, it is considered appropriate to use nonlinear viscoelastic and plastic (or viscoplastic) modeling. In this study, we focus only on the time dependence of monotonic loading, and attempt to model the nonlinear stress-strain behavior in the loading using linear viscoelastic and viscoplastic models approximately.

In the viscoelastic-viscoplastic model, the total strain ε is expressed as the sum of the viscoelastic strain ε^{VE} and the viscoplastic strain ε^{VP} .

$$\begin{aligned} \varepsilon &= \varepsilon^{VE} & (\sigma_{eq} < \sigma_Y) \\ \varepsilon &= \varepsilon^{VE} + \varepsilon^{VP} & (\sigma_{eq} > \sigma_Y) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

The viscoelastic strain ε^{VE} is 0 when the Mises equivalent stress σ_{eq} is lower than the yield stress σ_Y , which means only viscoelastic deformation. The viscoelastic constitutive model is defined as follows.

$$\sigma(t) = G(t) : \varepsilon(0) + \int G(t - \tau) : \dot{\varepsilon}^{ve}(\tau) d\tau \quad (2)$$

$$\text{with } \varepsilon(0) = \lim_{\substack{t \rightarrow 0 \\ t > 0}} \varepsilon(t) \text{ and } G(t) = 2G_R(t)I^{dev} + K_R(t)1 \otimes 1 \quad (3)$$

The shear modulus $G_R(t)$ and bulk modulus $K_R(t)$ are described using the generalized Maxwell model.

$$G_R(t) = G_0 \left[1 - \sum_{i=1}^n e_i \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\Lambda_k}} \right) \right] \quad (4)$$

$$K_R(t) = K_0 \left[1 - \sum_{i=1}^n e_i \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\Lambda_k}} \right) \right] \quad (5)$$

where G_0 is the initial shear modulus, and K_0 is the initial bulk modulus. To conduct a finite element analysis, the relaxation modulus (Prony series e_k, Λ_k) in equations (4) and (5) must be obtained from the results of creep tests for the cured TriA-X resin. In this research, the relaxation modulus was determined as follows. First, the creep test results at 20 MPa, where almost no residual strain occurs

after unloading, were fitted with a generalized Voigt model ($n=3$) as shown in Fig. 5. Next, the Prony series ($n=3$) was obtained by the Laplace transform for the Voigt model [13]. The determined Prony series are shown in Table 2.

Fig. 5: Relationship between creep compliance and time of TriA-X polyimide specimens at 23°C and 200°C.

Table 2: Prony series.

		23°C	200°C
Λ_1	[min]	1.91×10^{-1}	4.02×10^{-1}
Λ_2	[min]	6.07	5.44
Λ_3	[min]	1.14×10^2	1.08×10^2
e_1	[-]	8.30×10^{-2}	1.76×10^{-1}
e_2	[-]	4.10×10^{-2}	9.02×10^{-2}
e_3	[-]	5.66×10^{-2}	9.20×10^{-2}

The initial shear modulus G_0 and initial bulk modulus K_0 were calculated from Young's modulus E obtained in the monotonic tensile test using the following relationships.

$$K = \frac{E}{3(1 - 2\nu)} \quad (6)$$

$$G = \frac{E}{2(1 + \nu)} \quad (7)$$

where ν is Poisson's ratio, which is 0.37. The initial shear modulus and initial bulk modulus at each temperature are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Initial shear modulus, G_0 and initial bulk modulus, K_0 .

	23°C	200°C
G_0 [MPa]	1.20×10^3	6.98×10^2
K_0 [MPa]	4.20×10^3	2.45×10^3

3.2 Viscoplastic model

When the Mises stress σ_{eq} exceeds the yield stress σ_Y , plastic deformation occurs. The viscoplastic strain ε^{VP} was represented using the J_2 plasticity model as a time-dependent viscoplastic constitutive equation as follows;

$$\sigma_{eq} = \sigma_Y + R(p) \quad (8)$$

where $R(p)$ and p are hardening stress, and accumulated plastic strain, respectively. In this study, uniaxial tensile analysis is treated, therefore the Mises stress, σ_{eq} is equal to the axial stress, σ_{11} . $R(p)$ is approximated by the following power law.

$$R(p) = kp^{m_1} \quad (9)$$

where k is the hardening modulus and m_1 is the hardening exponent. The viscoplastic stress f is defined as follows.

$$f = \sigma_{eq} - \sigma_Y - R(p) \quad (10)$$

The accumulated plastic strain rate \dot{p} is expressed by the equation (11).

$$\dot{p} = \frac{\sigma_Y}{\eta} \left(\frac{f}{\sigma_Y} \right)^{m_2} \quad (11)$$

where η is the viscoplasticity coefficient, m_2 is the viscoplasticity index, σ_{eq} is the equivalent stress, and σ_Y is the yield stress. Substituting equations (9) and (10) into equation (11) and arranging,

$$\dot{p} = \frac{\sigma_Y}{\eta} \left(\frac{\sigma_{eq} - \sigma_Y - kp^{m_1}}{\sigma_Y} \right)^{m_2} \quad (12)$$

The constants k , m_1 , η and m_2 in Eq. (12) were determined by simultaneously fitting the experimental results of monotonic tensile tests, loading/unloading tests, and creep tests for cured TriA-X resins. As described in Chapter 2, TriA-X resin exhibits nonlinear viscoelastic behavior over a certain stress level, however, since only the monotonic loading is considered in this paper, linear viscoelasticity and viscoplasticity are applied in the model. Viscoplastic strain was calculated by subtracting the viscoelastic strain obtained from the 20 MPa test results from the creep strain measured at 60 MPa and 40 MPa at 23°C (RT) and 200°C, respectively. Table 4 shows the constants k , m_1 , η , m_2 and yield stress σ_Y obtained at room temperature and 200°C.

Table 4: Viscoplastic parameter.

	23°C	200°C
Hardening modulus, k [MPa]	211	230
Hardening exponent, m_1 [-]	0.465	0.615
Creep coefficient, η [MPa · s]	6.00×10^3	3.40×10^4
Creep exponent, m_2 [-]	2.8	13
Yield stress, σ_Y [MPa]	36.9	16.5

Fig. 6: Fitting of viscoplastic strain rate - viscoplastic strain curves at RT (23°C) and 200°C.

Fig. 7: Fitting of Stress Strain curves in 1 mm/min at RT (23°C) and 200°C.

4 NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS FOR NONLINEAR STRESS-STRAIN BEHAVIOR OF UNIDIRECTIONAL CFRP LAMINATES

4.1 Numerical Analysis Method

Tensile analysis of unidirectional reinforced CFRP in off-axis direction is conducted at 23°C and 200°C using a microscale representative volume element (RVE) model composed of matrix resin and fibers to predict the nonlinear stress-strain behavior of UD-CF/TriA-X. Digimat-FE (MSC Software, Hexagon) was used to make finite element model and set boundary conditions. Also, MS/Marc (MSC Software, Hexagon), standard solver of Digimat, was used for the finite element analysis (FEA). In order to simulate the tensile strength of unidirectional CFRP in the 30°, 45° and 90° directions, the REV models shown in Fig. 8 were made. The sizes of each model are presented in Table 5. All models are voxel meshes with hexahedral brick elements applied.

Table 5: RVE size and number of elements/nodes.

	30°	45°	90°
X (mm)	0.0154	0.0108	0.0764
Y (mm)	0.00889	0.0108	0.0764
Z (mm)	0.0133	0.0132	0.0132
Number of elements	125000	125000	125000
Number of nodes	132651	132651	132651

Fig. 8: Unit cell (RVE) model for microscale analysis.

Table 6: Material properties of carbon fiber, MR50 (Mitsubishi Chemical).

		Value
Fiber diameter	[mm]	0.006
Axial young's modulus E_{11}	[GPa]	2.95×10^2
In-plane young's modulus E_{22}	[GPa]	14
In-plane Poisson's ratio ν_{12}	[-]	0.2
Transverse Poisson's ratio ν_{23}	[-]	0.25
Transverse shear modulus G_{12}	[GPa]	27.6
Thermal expansion coefficient α_{carbon}	[K ⁻¹]	-4×10^{-7}

Table 6 shows the mechanical properties of the PAN-based carbon fiber (MR50, Mitsubishi Chemical Corporation) used in the calculations. The fibers were treated as isotropic elastic material. The fiber volume fraction is 0.56, in agreement with the experimental results. For the matrix resin, the viscoelastic/viscoplastic model defined in the previous section is applied, and it is assumed to be an isotropic material. The periodic boundary conditions are applied to each surface. The test condition in the analysis was strain control. To have the same strain rate as the experimental data, the loading rate was set to 0.0002083 [1/s]. Calculations were performed under the following two conditions (Case 1 and Case 2) for load and temperature to investigate the effect of thermal residual stress.

1. Mechanical load (Enforced displacement (strain) 1%) is applied at constant temperature (23°C, 200°C).
2. After giving the same temperature change of 370°C to 23°C as during processing, the temperature is maintained at the test temperature (23°C) and mechanical load (Enforced displacement (strain) 1%) is applied.

For the analysis of Case 2, the time-temperature superposition principle (TTSP) was applied to the viscoelastic model as follows;

$$\sigma(t) = \int_{-\infty}^t E(\tau - \dot{t}, T) : \frac{\partial \varepsilon^{ve}}{\partial \dot{t}} d\dot{t} \quad (13)$$

$$\text{With } E(t, T) = 3K_R(t, T)J + 2G_R(t, T)K \quad (14)$$

$$\Delta(t) = \int_0^t \frac{d\dot{t}}{A_T(T(\dot{t}))} \Rightarrow \frac{d\Delta}{dt} = \frac{1}{A_T(T(t))} \quad (15)$$

where A_T is the shift function in the time-temperature conversion law, using the Arrhenius law. Applying Eq. (15) to Δ_k in Eqs. (4) and (5), the temperature dependence of the relaxation modulus can be taken into account. The activation energy used in the Arrhenius equation was estimated from the master curve of the storage modulus at 30°C using the results of dynamic viscoelasticity (DMA) tests of resins from 30°C to 390°C. The estimated activation energy was 160 kJ/mol. In addition, the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) of the cured TriA-X is $6 \times 10^{-5} \text{ K}^{-1}$ [14].

4.1 Numerical Analysis Result

Stress-strain curves obtained from stress analysis for the 30°, 45°, and 90° directions and experimental results at room temperature obtained in the previous study are depicted in Fig. 9 (a), (b) and (c). The analytical results at room temperature were generally in good agreement with the experimental results, confirming that the analytical model was approximately valid.

A contour plot of plastic strain is presented in Fig. 10, immediately after cooling in Case 2. For all fiber orientation angles analyzed in this study, plastic strain was observed in the resin at close fiber spacing. In Fig. 9, when comparing the stress-strain curves at 23°C without (Case 1) and with (Case 2) thermal residual stress, significant differences were not observed. The possible reason for this is that in the model considering the thermal residual stress, although plastic deformation occurs once in the resin due to the difference in thermal shrinkage between the resin and the fiber, the time of increase in plastic strain is the same as in the model not considering the thermal residual stress. From these results, it is expected that there is little need to consider thermal residual stress at room temperature as well as 200°C, which is closer to the process temperature than room temperature.

Fig. 9: Numerical and experimental results of stress-strain curves of carbon fiber/TriA-X composites for 30°, 45°, 90° tensile test at 23°C and 200°C.

Fig. 10: Contour plot of plastic strain after cooling.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The mechanical properties of cured neat TriA-X resin are evaluated to model its stress-strain behavior, and the nonlinear mechanical behavior of UD- CF/TriA-X is predicted from stress analysis of a unit cell model consisting of fiber and matrix. The results obtained are as follows.

- (1) The viscoelastic-viscoplastic constitutive equation was applied to the cured TriA-X resin, and the necessary material parameters were determined from the tensile test results. The resin model created accurately reproduced the experimental results at both 23°C and 200°C.
- (2) The micro-scale analysis was conducted for the representative volume element model consisting of fiber and TriA-X matrix with applying the viscoelastic-viscoplastic model. The numerical results showed good agreement with the experimental results at room temperature. It was also confirmed that the effect of thermal residual stress during processing was relatively small for the tensile test results.

REFERENCES

- [1] M. K. Ghosh, and K. L. Mittal, *Polyimides: Fundamental and Applications*, Marcel Dekker, New York, 1996.
- [2] M. I. Bessonov, and V. A. Zubkov, *Polyamic Acids and Polyimides: Synthesis, Transformations and Structure*, CRC Press, Boca Raton, 1993.
- [3] C. Feger, M. M. Khojasteh, and S. E. Molis, *Polyimides: trends in Materials and Applications*, Society of Plastic Engineers, Mid Hudson Section, New York, 1996.
- [4] M. Tomoi, Fundamentals of thermosetting resin, *Journal of the institute of Electronics*, 4, 6, 2001, pp. 537-542.
- [5] T. T. Serafini, *Polyimides; Synthesis, Characterization, and Applications*, Vol. 2. Mittal, K. L., New York, Plenum, 1984.
- [6] M. Miyauchi, et al., Novel phenylethynyl-terminated PMDA-type polyimides based on KAPTON backbone structures derived from 2-phenyl-4,4'-diaminodiphenyl ether, *Journal of Polymer*, 44, 2012, pp. 959-965.
- [7] G. W. Meyer, B. Tan, J. E. McGrath, Solvent resistant polyetherimide network systems via phenylethynyl phthalic anhydride endcapping, *Journal of High Performance Polymers*, 6, 1994, pp. 423-435.
- [8] T. V. Holland, T. E. Glass, J. E. McGrath, Investigation of the thermal curing chemistry of the phenylethynyl group using a model aryl ether imide, *Polymer*, 41, 2000, pp. 4965-4990.
- [9] T. Takekoshi, J. M. Terry, High temperature thermoset polyimides containing disubstituted acetylene end groups, *Polymer*, 35, 1994, pp. 4874.
- [10] T. Ogasawara, Y. Ishida, and R. Yokota, *Journal of the Japan Society for Aeronautical and Space Sciences*, Vol. 54, 2006, pp. 161-167.
- [11] R. Minegishi, T. Ogasawara, T. Aoki, Y. Ishida, Nonlinear stress-strain behavior of unidirectional carbon fiber/ phenyl-ethynyl terminated KAPTON-type polyimide, TriA-X, composites at elevated temperatures, *Advanced Composite Materials*, 30, 2021, pp. 24-38.
- [12] J. N. Antonakakis, P. Bhargava, K. C. Chuang, A. T. Zehnder, Linear Viscoelastic Properties of HFPE-II-52 Polyimide, *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, 100, 2006, pp. 3255-3263.
- [13] S. P. Marques, G. J. Creus, *Computational viscoelasticity*, Springer Science & Business Media , 2012.
- [14] M. Sato, et al., Temperature dependence of interfacial strength of carbon-fiber-reinforced temperature-resistant polymer composites, *Composite Structure*, 202, 2018, pp. 283-289.